

Effectiveness of Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy on the level of Academic Procrastination among students studying in Nursing colleges of selected areas

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ABSTRACT

Academic procrastination is a pervasive issue among students in higher education and has been linked to poor academic performance, stress, and reduced psychological well-being. It is characterized by the voluntary delay of an intended course of action despite expecting to be worse off for the delay. Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy (REBT), a subtype of Cognitive Behavioural Therapy. REBT focuses on helping individuals identify and challenge irrational beliefs that contribute to emotional distress, replacing them with more rational, healthy ways of thinking. By addressing these thought patterns, individuals can better manage Procrastination. The objective of study was to assess effectiveness Effectiveness of Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy on the level of Academic Procrastination among students studying in Nursing colleges of selected areas.

METHOD: A quantitative research approach adopted .Quasi experimental pre test post test control group research design was used. . Tool has given to 100 students firstly for screening then a two group comprising 60 samples was selected by using a non-probability convenient sampling technique.30samples for experimental and 30 samples for control group. Experimental group received REBT and control group kept as it was. Data were collected by using Academic Procrastination scale. The paired t-test and two samples Z test was used. Analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics including fisher's exact test The accessible population selected for this study consisted of Nursing students with academic procrastination As an intervention REBT implemented. , it was evident that the REBT Method was significantly effective in reducing academic procrastination and improving academic performance among Nursing students.

RESULT: Screening showed that 40% of nursing students had mild, 4% moderate, and 56% severe academic procrastination. In the experimental group, most students had severe academic procrastination at pretest, which improved to mild (23.3%) and moderate (76.7%) levels after Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy (REBT). No improvement was observed in the control group. The mean procrastination score reduced from 72.6 (pretest) to 45.6 (posttest) with a significant paired t-test value ($t = 18.7, p < 0.05$). Two-sample z-test also showed significant improvement in the experimental group compared to the control group ($z = 18, p < 0.05$). No demographic variables showed significant association with academic procrastination.

KEYWORDS: Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy (REBT), Academic Procrastination.

INTRODUCTION

Academic procrastination is voluntarily or needlessly delaying an academic task to an indefinite time, which is needed to be completed at an assigned time. Studies show that most university students procrastinate in their academic situations because they believe it is a characteristic of their academic activities (Karmen et al., 2015) also Argiropoulou & Ferrari, (2014) revealed that 75% of students postponed their tasks frequently due to academic difficulties. College students need to devote most of their time to completing different academic-related tasks like submitting assignments, projects, writing papers, note-making, participating in extracurricular activities, etc so they intentionally or unintentionally engage in delaying behaviour as they need to complete all the tasks within a short period are very common among university students as they have a multitude of academic requirements like research work, engaging in group discussion, etc. Students generally procrastinate for various reasons such as lack of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, communication gap, illness, too much work, lack of guidance, home environments, and lack of coordination, work inability, unseen problem, teacher's attitude, perfectionism, negative comment, task evasiveness, dependence on technology and others.

Academic procrastination is a pervasive issue among students in higher education and has been linked to poor academic performance, stress, and reduced psychological well-being. It is characterized by the voluntary delay of an intended course of action despite expecting to be worse off for the delay.

Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy (REBT), a subtype of Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT), developed by psychologist Albert Ellis. REBT focuses on helping individuals identify and challenge irrational beliefs that contribute to emotional distress, replacing them with more rational, healthy ways of thinking. By addressing these thought patterns, individuals can better manage Procrastination.

Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy (REBT), developed by Albert Ellis, is a cognitive-behavioural approach that focuses on identifying and changing irrational beliefs that lead to emotional and behavioural issues, including procrastination. REBT helps individuals challenge maladaptive thought patterns and replace them with rational and constructive thinking, thereby promoting behavioural change. The therapeutic approach has been found effective in reducing academic procrastination and enhancing time management skills and academic performance among university students.

METHODS:

Study Design: Quasi experimental pre test post test control group research design

Research Approach: The research methodology adopted for the study employed a quantitative research approach.

Setting: Nursing colleges of selected areas.

Sampling technique: Non-probability, convenient sampling technique.

Population: Nursing students with Academic procrastination

Study Protocol: Before the data collection, consent was taken from the participants. The pre-test was conducted before the implementation of the intervention REBT. Data was collected from 23/12/2025 to 19/01/2026.

Data collection:

Section A – Semi-structured Questionnaire was prepared by the investigator which includes questions regarding demographic variables: Age group, Gender, Course, Type of family, income Use of Social Media, Parents education status, Birth order and Living area.

Section B – This consist of finalized tool that is Academic Procrastination Scale is a tool used to assess the level of Academic procrastination experienced by a student's before and after the intervention. It is a subjective measure, where the students rates their academic procrastination level on a scale from 0 to 100, 0-33 mild, 33-66 moderate, 67-100 severe higher total scores indicate a greater tendency toward academic procrastination, while lower scores reflect better self-regulation, planning, and study habits. This scale is commonly used in educational and psychological research to understand students' study patterns and to evaluate the effectiveness of interventions aimed at reducing procrastination.

METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

1. Approval from the research committee members and written permission from the head of the institution to conduct study was obtained.
2. Purpose of the research was explained to the participants.
3. Informed consent (written) was explained to the participants.
4. Formal permission was obtained from the concerned authority. Subjects were taken from the selected Nursing College students using non-probability convenient sampling technique. The investigator introduced themselves and informed the samples about the nature of the study to ensure better co-operation during the data collection. Objectives of the study and confidentiality of the data was discussed.
5. The data gathering process began from 23/12/25 to 19/01/26
6. Each subject was given a prepared tool containing
 - Section A – Consent form.
 - Section B - Tool for demographic variables.
 - Section C – Academic Procrastination scale

Statistical Methods

Descriptive statistics: Frequency and percentage distribution were used to describe demographic variables. Mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the pre-test and post-test.

Inferential statistics: Paired t-test for the effectiveness of REBT on Academic procrastination among students studying in Nursing colleges of selected areas. Fisher's exact test for association between selected demographic variables.

Data analysis:

Sample size: The formula used for sample size is

Sample size is the number of observations or individuals included in a study.

The formula used for sample size is

$$n = Z_{\alpha/2}^2 * (SD^2) / MOE^2,$$

$$n = (1.96)^2 * (2.2)^2 / (0.85)^2$$

$$n = 3.8416 * 4.84 / 0.7225$$

$$n=18.59/0.7225$$

$$n= 25.73$$

Where, $Z_{\alpha/2}$ is the critical value of the Normal distribution at $\alpha/2$ (e.g. for a confidence level of 95%, α is 0.05 and the critical value is 1.96),

MOE is the margin of error,

SD is the standard deviation from previous study.

For our calculations,

$$Z_{\alpha/2}=1.96$$

$$SD=2.2.$$

$$MOE=0.85$$

The sample size, n comes to be 26, so you can take 30 samples in each group considering drop outs.

ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA:

Inclusion criteria:

Students currently studying in 2nd to 6th semester B.sc Nursing students.

Students' participation based on screening criteria that is score more than 34 and previous academic performance.

Exclusion criteria:

Students currently undergoing structured psychotherapy, counselling, or other behavioural interventions.

Students on medications that may affect cognitive and behavioural responses.

Withdrawal criteria:

Samples can withdraw from research at any point of time during the data collection.

RESULTS:

Screening of Pre-existing level of Academic Procrastination among students studying in Nursing colleges of selected areas

n=100

Academic Procrastination	Freq	%
Mild	40	40.0%
Moderate	4	4.0%
Severe	56	56.0%

During screening phase, 40% of the Nursing students had mild academic procrastination, 4% of them had moderate academic procrastination and 56% of them had severe academic procrastination.

Fig. 4.1 A Pie diagram showing percentage distribution of Academic procrastination among Nursing students at Screening.

Description of samples (Nursing students) based on their demographic variables

Age group: In experimental group, 40% of the Nursing students had age 19-20 years, 36.7% of them had age 20.1-21 years and 23.3% of them had age 21.1-22 years. In control group, 40% of the Nursing students had age 19-20 years, 36.7% of them had age 20.1-21 years and 23.3% of them had age 21.1-22 years.

Gender: In experimental group, 43.3% of them were males and 56.7% of them were females. In control group, 50% of them were males and 50% of them were females.

Course: In experimental group, 20% of them were studying in B.Sc. Second semester, 33.3% of them were studying in B.Sc. 3rd semester, 20% of them were studying in B.Sc. 4th semester, 16.7% of them were studying in B.Sc. 5th semester and 10% of them were studying in B.Sc. 6th semester. In control group, 10% of them were studying in B.Sc. Second semester, 30% of them were studying in B.Sc. 3rd semester, 26.7% of them were studying in B.Sc. 4th semester, 20% of them were studying in B.Sc. 5th semester and 13.3% of them were studying in B.Sc. 6th semester.

Type of family: In experimental group, 16.7% of them had extended family, 46.7% of them had nuclear family and 36.7% of them had joint family. In control group, 20% of them had extended family, 33.3% of them had nuclear family and 46.7% of them had joint family.

Family income: In experimental group, 6.7% of them had family income less than Rs.10000, 33.3% of them had family income Rs.15000-20000, 20% of them had family income Rs. 20000-25000 and 40% of them had family income above Rs. 25000. In control group, 10% of them had family income less than Rs.10000, 23.3% of them had family income Rs.15000-20000, 26.7% of them had family income Rs. 20000-25000 and 40% of them had family income above Rs. 25000.

Use of social media: In experimental group, 3.3% of them were using social media for 1 to 2 hours, 13.3% of them were using social media for 3 to 4 hours, 33.3% of them were using

social media for 5 to 6 hours and 50% of them were using social media for more than 6 hours. In control group, 6.7% of them were using social media for 1 to 2 hours, 3.3% of them were using social media for 3 to 4 hours, 33.3% of them were using social media for 5 to 6 hours and 56.7% of them were using social media for more than 6 hours.

Parent's education status: In experimental group, 30% of them were illiterate and 70% of them were literate. In control group, 36.7% of them were illiterate and 63.3% of them were literate.

Birth order: In experimental group, 23.3% of them were oldest child, 46.7% of them were middle child and 30% of them were youngest child. In control group, 33.3% of them were oldest child, 43.3% of them were middle child and 23.3% of them were youngest child.

Living area: In experimental group, 60% of them were living in hostel, 23.3% of them were living at home and 16.7% of them were living as paying guest. In control group, 53.3% of them were living in hostel, 30% of them were living at home and 16.7% of them were living as paying guest.

Analysis of data related to pre-existing level of Academic Procrastination among students studying in Nursing colleges of selected areas

Table 4.3: Pre-existing level of Academic Procrastination among students studying in Nursing colleges of selected areas

n=30, 30

Academic Procrastination	Experimental		Control	
	Pretest		Pretest	
	Freq	%	Freq	%
Mild	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
Moderate	4	13.3%	0	0.0%
Severe	26	86.7%	30	100.0%

In experimental group, 13.3% of the Nursing students had moderate Academic Procrastination and 86.7% of them had severe Academic Procrastination. In control group, all of them had severe Academic Procrastination.

Fig. 4.11 A bar diagram showing percentage distribution of pretest level of academic procrastination in experimental and control group

Section IV

Analysis of data related to the Effectiveness of Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy on the level of Academic procrastination among students studying in Nursing colleges of selected areas

Table 4.4: Effectiveness of Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy on the level of Academic procrastination among students studying in Nursing colleges of selected areas

n=30, 30

Academic Procrastination	Experimental				Control			
	Pretest		Posttest		Pretest		Posttest	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
Mild	0	0.0%	7	23.3%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
Moderate	4	13.3%	23	76.7%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
Severe	26	86.7%	0	0.0%	30	100.0%	30	100.0%

In experimental group, in pretest, 13.3% of the Nursing students had moderate Academic Procrastination and 86.7% of them had severe Academic Procrastination. In post test, 23.3% of them had mild Academic Procrastination and 76.7% of them had moderate Academic Procrastination. In control group, in pretest and post test, all of them had severe Academic Procrastination. This indicates that there is remarkable improvement in the academic procrastination among Nursing students after Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy.

Fig 4.12 A bar diagram showing percentage distribution of pretest and post- test level of academic procrastination in experimental and control group

Table 4.5: Paired t-test for the effectiveness of Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy on the level of Academic procrastination among students studying in Nursing colleges of selected areas

n=30.30

	Mean	SD	T	df	p-value
Pretest	72.6	6.1	18.7	29	0.000
Posttest	45.6	9.6			

Researcher applied Paired t-test for the effectiveness of Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy on the level of Academic procrastination among students studying in Nursing colleges of selected areas. Average Academic procrastination score among Nursing students in pretest was 72.6 which reduced to 45.6 in posttest. T-value for this test was 18.7 with 29 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected. Average Academic procrastination score in posttest was significantly less than that in pretest. It is evident that the Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy is significantly effective in reducing the Academic procrastination among Nursing students.

Fig 4.13 A bar diagram showing average academic procrastination score among Nursing students n experimental group in pre test and post test

Table 4.6: Two sample z-test for the comparison of change in Academic procrastination among Nursing students in experimental and control group

n=30, 30

Group	Mean	SD	Z	p-value
Experimental	27.0	7.9	18	0.000
Control	0.9	0.7		

Researcher applied Two sample z-test for the comparison of change in Academic procrastination among Nursing students in experimental and control group. Average change Academic procrastination score among Nursing students in experimental group was 27 which was 0.9 in control group. Z-value for this test was 18. Corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected. Average change in academic procrastination score in posttest was significantly higher than that in control group. It is evident that the Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy is significantly effective in reducing the Academic procrastination among Nursing students.

Fig. 4.14 A bar diagram showing average change in academic procrastination score among Nursing students in experimental and control group

Analysis of data related to association between Academic procrastination with selected demographic variables

Table 4.7: Fisher’s exact test for the association between Academic procrastination with selected demographic variables

n=60

Demographic variable		Academic Procrastination		p-value
		Moderate	Severe	
Age	19-20 years	0	24	0.224
	20.1-21 years	2	17	
	21.1-22 years	2	15	
Gender	Male	0	28	0.116
	Female	4	28	
Course	BSC 2nd semester	0	9	0.848
	BSC 3rd semester	1	18	
	BSC 4th semester	1	13	
	BSC 5th semester	1	10	
	BSC 6th semester	1	6	
Type of family	Extended	0	11	0.512
	Nuclear	1	23	
	Joint	3	22	
Family income	<Rs. 10,000	0	5	1.000
	Rs. 15,000 - 20,000	1	16	
	Rs. 20,000-25,000	1	13	

	> Rs. 25,000	2	22	
Use Social Media	1 to 2 hours	0	3	0.230
	3 to 4 hours	1	4	
	5 to 6 hours	0	20	
	More than 6 hours	3	29	
Parents education status	Illiterate	1	19	1.000
	Literate	3	37	
Birth order	Oldest child	1	16	0.571
	Middle child	3	24	
	Youngest child	0	16	
Living Area	Hostel	2	32	0.620
	Home	2	14	
	Paying guest	0	10	

Since all the p-values were large (greater than 0.05), none of the demographic variables was found to have significant association with the Academic Procrastination among Nursing students.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

On the basis of the present study, the investigator suggested the following recommendations.

- A similar study may be replicated on large samples thereby findings can be generalized.
- The study can be replicated in different settings.
- The study can be replicated by changing the samples for the study.
- An experimental study can be performed using different types of interventions.
- A similar study can be conducted with different research designs and large samples.

ABBREVIATIONS:

CVI	Content Validity Index
CVR	Content Validity Ratio
MOE	Margin of Error
N	Number of Experts on Panel
n	Total number of samples
Freq.	Frequency
SD	Standard Deviation
T	Test Statistic
df	Degree of Freedom
p-value	Probability Value
r	number of pairs of scores of sample,
Σxy	sum of x scores,
Σy	sum of squared x scores,
REBT	Rational Emotive behaviour Therapy

REFERENCES

- 1.Karmen M, King S, Pennington R. Procrastination and academic performance among university students. *J Educ Psychol*. 2015;107(3):602–614.
2. Ferrari JR, Johnson JL, McCown WG. *Procrastination and task avoidance: Theory, research, and treatment*. New York: Springer; 1995.
- 3.Ellis A. *Reason and emotion in psychotherapy*. New York: Lyle Stuart; 1962.
- 4.Ellis A, Dryden W. *The practice of rational emotive behavior therapy*. 2nd ed. New York: Springer; 1997
5. Chakraborty MU, Ahmed MS, Soundararajan MS. Academic Procrastination Among College Students Living with Family and Living Away from Family. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*. 2022 Nov 5;10(1).<https://ijip.co.in/index.php/ijip/article/view/578>
- 6.Bhusal N. Academic Procrastination's Antecedents and their Predictability on College Students in Kathmandu Valley. *Journal of Balkumari College*. 2023 Dec 7;12(1):20-9.
<http://balkumaricollege.edu.np/journal>
7. 13.Boruah T, Padmavathy RD. A study on relationship between Academic Procrastination and Emotional Intelligence among University Students of India. *NeuroQuantology*. 2022;20(10):6421.
8. Joshy A, Chacko N. Procrastination, Study Habits and Optimistic Attitude among College Students. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*. 2021;9(2).
<https://ijip.co.in/index.php/ijip/article/view/1346>